

Eye as a Window for Systemic Diseases: A Case Series**Kavita Patil¹, Rajeshwari Mahantgol², Haritha. V³, Aarti³**¹Professor and Head of the Department, Department of Ophthalmology, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi, Karnataka, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi, Karnataka, India³Junior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi, Karnataka, India

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Eyes are frequently involved in various systemic diseases affecting the rest of the body. Ocular manifestations in certain multisystem disorders will be initial manifestation & may offer a diagnostic clue.**Materials & Methods:** Case series study of 13 patients of different age groups attended the Department of Ophthalmology, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences.**Discussion:** Diagnostic approaches including ophthalmic examination techniques, imaging modalities and laboratory tests are discussed to enhance diagnostic accuracy.**Conclusion:** Recognising the ocular manifestations earliest is crucial for early diagnosis, timely intervention and effective management of systemic diseases.**Keywords:** imaging modalities, diagnosis.

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Introduction

The eyes, can offer critical clues to diagnosis of various systemic illnesses [1]. Many systemic diseases present with ocular symptoms that can precede or accompany other clinical signs, offering valuable insights into a patient's overall health [2]. This comprehensive review aims to elucidate the complex interplay between ocular manifestations and systemic conditions, emphasising importance of early recognition and interdisciplinary collaboration in diagnosis and patient management [2].

This review encompasses various systemic diseases including autoimmune, infectious, endocrine, genetic, dermatological, cardiovascular, neurological, haematological, renal and connective tissue disorders highlighting their specific ocular manifestations. All of the inherited vascular disorders have associated ocular findings [3]. Moreover, the growing prevalence of chronic diseases accentuates the need for increases awareness and understanding of their ocular implications [4].

This study aims to improve clinical practice, promote integrative healthcare, enhance patient outcome by providing detailed overview of ocular manifestations that help in diagnosis of systemic diseases [5].

Methods and Materials

Case series study of 13 patients of different age groups attended the Ophthalmology OPD in tertiary care centre between January 2023 to June 2023 with majority being females. Demographic data and history was obtained. Visual acuity, slit lamp examination, funduscopy and other required imaging techniques were obtained.

To elicit the importance of ocular examination as an essential diagnostic component of any physical examination.

Results and Discussion**Autoimmune diseases:**

1) A 45-year-old female with diminution of vision both eyes since 6 months.

O/E: BCVA 6/24, Schirmer's type1 - 5mm, Tear film breakup time of 5 seconds (Image 1) both eyes with oral sicca diagnosed as Primary Sjogren's syndrome with positive Anti-SSA and SSB antibodies, referred to physician and started on oral corticosteroids in a tapering dose.

Image 1: Tear film breakup time test

2) A 62-year-old female with intense pain and diminution of vision in right eye since a week.

O/E: BCVA 6/60, diffuse scleritis (Image 2) and keratouveitis with RA factor positive diagnosed as Rheumatoid arthritis, referred to rheumatologist and started on Tab. Hydroxychloroquine 200mg once a day and follow up every 2 weeks.

Image 2: Diffuse scleritis

Infectious Diseases:

3) A 45-year-old female with headache and diminution of vision since 15 days.

O/E: BCVA 6/12, Exudative Retinal Detachment of right eye (Image 3) with Mantoux test positive (12mm), ESR – 102mm/hr & CRP- 14 mg/dl and Chest x ray PA view with miliary tubercles diagnosed as Pulmonary Koch's, referred to Pulmonologist, started on Anti Tubercular Therapy and advised regular follow-up.

Image 3: Exudative retinal detachment

4) 28 years old male patient with sudden onset of redness and dull aching pain in the right eye followed by diminution of vision with perception of black spots and intolerance to light.

O/ E: Mutton fat keratic precipitates on corneal endothelium (Image 4) with iris nodules at pupillary border with vitreous cells both eyes and fundus showing perivascular sheathing with multiple chorioretinal nodules (Image 5) suggestive of Bilateral granulomatous pan uveitis with raised angiotensin converting enzyme levels [6] diagnosed as pulmonary sarcoidosis, referred to physician and started on oral glucocorticoids.

Image 4: Mutton fat KP

Image 5: Chorioretinal nodules

5) A 55-year-old male with nodular ulcerative growth on temporal part of bulbar conjunctiva encroaching onto cornea with BCVA 6/9 suggestive of Ocular surface squamous neoplasia (Image 6). OSSN is commonly associated with HIV infection. So, on screening patient turned out to be HIV positive, started on Anti-Retroviral Therapy with excisional biopsy & local mitomycin C application.

Image 6: OSSN

Genetic Conditions:

6) 40-Year-old male with gradual painless diminution of vision left eye since 2 years associated with headache holocranial.

His BCVA 6/ 24 in left eye. Dilated fundus of left eye showed grossly enlarged feeder vessels leading to angiomatous peripheral lesion in the supertemporal quadrant suggestive of retinal capillary hemangioblastoma (Image 7).

MRI BRAIN PLAIN: Cerebellar haemangioma in the superior aspect (Image 8).

USG ABDOMEN AND PELVIS: Bilateral simple renal cortical cysts suggestive of Von Hippel Lindau syndrome, referred to neurosurgeon for tumour excision.

Image 7: Retinal capillary haemangioma

Image 8: Cerebellar haemangioma

7) A 33-year-old male with diminution of vision both eyes since 15yrs.

O/E: BCVA CF 1m, Supertemporal subluxation of cataractous lens (Image 9) with long slender fingers, hands & feet and aortic dissection on 2DEcho for which he got operated diagnosed as Marfan's syndrome, referred to cardiologist and got operated for endovascular stent-graft repair.

Image 9: Superotemporal subluxation of lens

8) 28year old male patient presented with gradual painless progressive diminution of vision both eyes since 10 years.

O/E: BCVA 5/60 both eyes with -40 D sphere and -2.25 D cylindrical power. Anterior segment evaluation shows Anterior and posterior lenticonus (Image 10). On ear evaluation patient had moderate sensory neural hearing loss and urine examination shows moderate proteinuria and hematuria suggestive of Alport syndrome referred to nephrologist and advised for regular follow-up.

Image 10: Anterior & posterior lenticonus

Dermatological Conditions:

9) A 25-year-old female with BCVA 6/9 & 6/60 in right & left eye.

O/E: blepharitis with Salzmann nodular degeneration (Image 11) in both eyes (left > right) & lesions over face diagnosed as Acne Rosacea, advised lid hygiene with topical lubricants referred to dermatologist, started on oral tetracyclines and topical sun blocking agents.

Image 11: Salzmann nodular degeneration

Neurological Conditions:

10) A 49-year-old female with BCVA 6/60, O/E: Hyperaemic disc of right eye with hard exudates (Image 12) surrounding disc and CT brain showing Frontal lobe Meningioma and referred to neurosurgeon and operated for the same.

Image 12: Hyperaemic disc with edema and hard exudates

11) A 53 years old male patient presented with recurrent optic neuritis, urinary retention and lower back pain.

On examination: BCVA: Perception of light, defective colour vision, RAPD seen. Fundoscopy suggestive of optic neuritis (Image 13) in 1st attack treated with Inj. Methylprednisolone 1g IV for 3 days and tapered with steroids and retrobulbar neuritis in second attack, treated with inj. Methylprednisolone 1g IV.

Blood investigations were normal and imaging was suggestive of transverse myelitis diagnosed as Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorder referred to neurologist and advised inj. Methylprednisolone 500mg IV infusion weekly for 8 weeks followed by cyclophosphamide or rituximab.

Image 13: Optic neuritis

12) 40 years old female patient with h/o episodic transient obscuration of vision in both eyes which lasts for few seconds since 20 days associated with flashes of light, headache giddiness and decreased hearing.

O/E: lagophthalmos in right eye with BCVA: 6/9 and marked disc edema in both eyes. On imaging diagnosed as Vestibular Schwannoma on right side (Image 14), referred to neurosurgeon and subtotal excision of tumour was done.

Image 14: Vestibular schwannoma

Metabolic Conditons:

13) A 38yr old female with sudden painless diminution of vision in right eye 6 months back.

O/E: BCVA Hand movements close to face, grade 3 RAPD, Neovascularisation of iris at 9 '0' clock with pale disc and box carrying of superotemporal vessels suggestive of Central Retinal Artery Occlusion (Image 15) with serum homocysteine levels of 36mcmol/ diagnosed as Hyperhomocysteinemia referred to physician and started on folate and cobalamin supplementation.

Image 15: Pale disc with box carring of vessels

Conclusion

Most of the systemic diseases manifests with ocular manifestations for the first time. Ocular manifestations often serve as indicators of underlying valuable diagnostic and prognostic information as well as early diagnosis and management.

List of Abbreviations:

BCVA: Best corrected visual acuity

RA factor: rheumatoid factor

ESR: Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate

CRP: C- Reactive protein

RAPD: relative afferent pupillary defect

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